

Preliminary Design of a Deep Offshore Airborne Wind Energy Farm

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1. Preliminary Design

The objective of this preliminary design phase is twofold:

1. To provide a foundation for the techno-economic analysis, assessing the costs of components, ultimately determining the feasibility and competitiveness of the OAWF system.
2. To develop a comprehensive inventory for the LCA, enabling the evaluation of environmental impacts associated with each component and the overall system.

The design of the OAWF system shown in Figure ?? will include the sizing of critical components, such as the kite and tether, which are central to the energy generation process, as well as the floating platforms and mooring lines, which are essential for ensuring stability and functionality in offshore deployment. In particular, we are going to follow the simplified one-dimensional model described in [1]. In addition to these core elements, the offshore deployment necessitates integrating electrical machinery and transmission lines to facilitate energy conversion and transfer for an offshore farm configuration.

Figure 1: Sketch of Deep Offshore Airborne Wind Energy systems with their main sub-systems.

1.1. Kite and Tether

At the time this paper was written, no dominant design has emerged for AWE aircraft wings [2], with on-ground generation systems spanning from higher-efficiency rigid wings to lighter and cheaper soft-wing kites. We focus on the soft-wing kite since a preliminary design is sufficient to have a reasonable estimate of its mass.

The sizing of such a system begins with the power requirement and the wind distribution data. While the former is the result of both market analysis and mission objective, the latter is given by the investigated site. In this case, we select the maximum reel-out power¹ of one unit to be 2 MW. This choice is justified by the average traditional wind turbine power rating [3] and the trade-off between the requisite of large-scale energy production and the resulting size for a soft-wing kite - about 70 m of wingspan for the preliminary

¹The maximum reel-out power is equivalent to the generator rated power.

design achieved in this study, as described later. We identify a site in Sicily, Italy, west of Egadi islands (37°58'N, 11°33'E), to provide a relevant reference point for environmental footprint comparison with a traditional wind farm, as discussed in Section ???. Wind data for this location are retrieved from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset [4]. To estimate wind speeds at higher altitudes where direct data were unavailable for this specific site, we utilize the hourly wind speed values at the standard reference heights of 10 m and 100 m. These two data points allow for a site-specific fit of the wind profile power law:

$$V_{w,H} = V_{w,0} \left(\frac{H}{H_0} \right)^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where $V_{w,H}$ is the wind speed at height H , $V_{w,0}$ is the wind speed at reference height H_0 , and α is an empirical coefficient that characterizes the wind profile. The extrapolated wind data at 200 m of altitude result in a Weibull Probability Density Function (PDF) for the wind speed with a scale parameter of 8.7 and a shape parameter equal to 1.7. We consider the latter altitude to be the altitude at which the system's performance is evaluated. This choice is carried out by considering an average altitude over the whole operating altitude range.

To determine the characteristic curves and performance of the system, we adopt a simplified kite model with the following assumptions: (a) steady-state flight, (b) negligible mass of the flying device, (c) straight tether, and (d) wind speed V_w parallel to the ground. By using the governing equations first derived by Loyd [5] and later refined by Trevisi et al. [6], we can evaluate the tether tension T :

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \rho (V_w \cos(\beta) - V_{out})^2 (1 + G^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} A \frac{C_L}{G} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the air density, V_{out} is the tether reel-out velocity, G is the lift-to-drag ratio, C_L is the lift coefficient, β is the tether elevation angle, and A is the kite area.

The power generated during the reel-out phase is $P = TV_{out}$.

The drag coefficient is given by Eq. 3

$$C_D = C_{D_0} + \frac{C_L^2}{\pi AR \cdot e} + \frac{C_\perp d_t l_t}{4A} \quad (3)$$

where the first term represents the parasite drag, the second one the induced drag, and the third is the drag caused by the tether. In particular,

AR is the aspect ratio of the kite, e is the Oswald coefficient, d_t and l_t are the diameter and length of the tether, respectively, and C_{\perp} is the drag coefficient of the tether.

Symbol	Value	Description
β	20°	Tether elevation angle
C_L	0.6	Lift coefficient
A	1200 m ²	Wing surface area
C_{D_0}	0.088	Wing parasite drag coefficient
AR	4	Aspect ratio
e	0.9	Oswald coefficient
C_{\perp}	1	Tether drag coefficient
l_t	1000 m	Tether length*
d_t	0.05 m	Tether diameter
T_{max}	1899 kN	Maximum tether tension
SF	3	Tether safety factor
AEP	3.40 GWh	Annual Energy Production
CF	0.39	Capacity Factor

Table 1: Top part: design parameters of the investigated kite wing. Bottom part: performance parameters of a single kite

* In the table, the total length of the tether is reported to consider operations well above 200 m of altitude. For the design point evaluation, a tether length of 600 m was considered - this choice can be considered a conservative assumption to take into account the additional drag due to the tether sag.

In the upper portion of Table 1, we report the parameters used in the sizing and characterization of the system. While β and C_L correspond to typical operating conditions, the wing surface area A is purposely adopted to meet the rated power requirement at a relatively low rated wind speed.

C_{D_0} is obtained considering a lift-to-drag ratio of the wing alone² around 5 [7]. The low aspect ratio AR of the flexible wing is computed considering the geometrical data of TU Delft’s demonstrator *LEI V3 Kite* [7], producing a wing span of 69.3 m. Values for e and C_{\perp} are those commonly employed in the literature [8, 9].

DYNEEMA®[®], a strong light-weight synthetic fiber of UHMWPE, widely adopted in the AWE sector [2], is designated as the tether material. Its diameter is selected from a catalogue of solutions available [10] considering the stresses involved; its tensile strength is derived accordingly. We impose a safety factor of 3 for the tether tension to prevent excessive wear and diminish its replacement frequency.

Given a range of operative wind speeds between 3 m/s and 25 m/s, we can obtain the characteristic curve of power for the reel-out phase (in blue in Figure 2). In the very first phase of power production, the system operates at its optimal reel-out velocity. When the maximum power limit is reached, one parameter between the lift coefficient C_L and the reel-out velocity V_{out} needs to be controlled. To limit the tether fatigue, we formulate an optimization problem with the double constraint of maximum power and decreasing tether tension. The power curve over a cycle (in red in Figure 2) is then derived by multiplying the reel-out power by 0.5, assumed to be the cycle efficiency³ [11]. By combining this curve with the wind PDF, we compute the Annual Energy Production (*AEP*) of a single kite and its Capacity Factor (*CF*) to be equal to 3.40 GWh and 0.39, respectively, as reported in the lower portion of Table 1.

Regarding the bill of materials, the wing is composed of two layers of Dacron (188 g/m²), a polyester fabric commonly used for sails. Additionally, we consider a coating of titanium dioxide (26 g/m²) against UV radiation, a requirement that is found in the literature to prevent the fabric degradation [12]. As for the tether, the 50 mm-diameter commercial UHMWPE features a linear density of 1.318 kg/m [10].

1.2. Floating Platform and Mooring Lines

The considered Sicilian site is characterised by water depths exceeding 50 meters, thus requiring floating platforms instead of fixed-bottom ones [13].

²Lift-to-drag ratio obtained by considering only the first two terms of drag in Eq. 3.

³In a first approximation, this efficiency is considered to be independent of the wind speed.

Figure 2: Power curve of a single OAW system considered in this study

Figure 3 illustrates various floating platform configurations. The spar-buoy type is particularly advantageous in sites with water depths exceeding 50 meters.

Figure 3: Different typologies of floating platforms (from [14])

Key design parameters include cylinder dimensions, material properties and port assembly constraints. While the study focuses on cylindrical designs, it must be acknowledged that other geometries for spar buoy platforms exist.

In the approach followed by Cherubini *et al.* [1], three main sizes are taken into consideration, as shown in Figure 4.

The following analysis aims at selecting the proper size given the wave distribution of the Sicilian site.

Figure 4: Dimensions of the three candidate platform models (adapted from [1])

We retrieved wave data from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset [4]. In Figure 5 the period probability distribution is shown.

To assess the platform’s hydrodynamic response, we then applied the linear potential flow theory and the linear theory of waves [15]. The first theory simplifies fluid dynamics by assuming inviscid, incompressible, and irrotational flow, while the second consists of a mathematical framework used to describe the behaviour of water waves in a linearised and simplified manner.

With these ingredients, we can model the wave profile $\eta(t)$ and excitation forces $f_e(\eta(t))$ as

$$\eta(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N A_n \sin(\omega_n t + \theta_n) \quad (4)$$

$$f_e(\eta(t)) = \sum_{n=1}^N |f_{e,n}| A_n \sin(\omega_n t + \theta_n + \phi_n) \quad (5)$$

Figure 5: Wave period probability distribution in the Sicilian coast [4]

where ω_n is the angular frequency of the n -th wave component, θ_n is the phase of the n -th wave component, $|f_{e,n}|$ the magnitude of the excitation force for the n -th wave component, and ϕ_n is the phase shift between the wave profile and the excitation force. We can compute $|f_{e,n}|$ using linear potential theory, including both Froude–Krylov and diffraction contributions, in particular by using a boundary element method (BEM) frequency-domain solver, namely Nemoh. We define the amplitude A_n for each component of the JONSWAP spectrum which is a commonly used empirical wave spectrum that describes the energy distribution of ocean waves as a function of their frequency. [16]

The platform’s response is modeled using the Cummins equation

$$(M + A_\infty)\ddot{x} + \int_0^t K_r(t - \tau)\dot{x} d\tau + B_\nu|\dot{x}|\dot{x} + K_h x = f_e(\eta(t)) + f_{ext}(t, x, \dot{x}) \quad (6)$$

where:

- M = mass of the platform, A_∞ = added mass
- \ddot{x} = platform acceleration, \dot{x} = velocity, x = displacement
- $\int_0^t K_r(t - \tau)\dot{x} d\tau$ = radiation force, $K_r(t - \tau)$ = retardation function,
- $B_\nu|\dot{x}|\dot{x}$ = viscous damping force, B_ν = viscous damping coefficient,
- $K_h x$ = hydrostatic restoring force, K_h = hydrostatic stiffness coefficient,
- $f_e(\eta(t))$ = excitation force due to wave profile $\eta(t)$,
- $f_{ext}(t, x, \dot{x})$ = external forces (e.g., wind, current).

In order to evaluate the hydrodynamic characteristics, we used NEMOH [17], a Boundary Element Methods (BEM) code dedicated to the computation of first order wave loads on offshore structures. The procedure consists on discretizing the wetted surface of the floater with plane mesh panels, and in each panel the boundary equations from the potential flow theory are written and solved for each single wave frequency and degree of freedom.

Based on the evaluation of the time and frequency responses for the three platform models, we select the platform with a diameter of 5 meters as the most suitable option for the Sicilian site, given the absence of resonance phenomena.

Using Archimedes' principle, we calculated the required ballast and hull masses using the following equation,

$$V_{\text{steel}}\rho_{\text{steel}} + V_{\text{ballast}}\rho_{\text{ballast}} + m_{\text{AWE}} = V_{\text{immersed}}\rho_{\text{water}} \quad (7)$$

where

- V_{steel} is the volume of the steel structure,
- ρ_{steel} is the density of steel,

- V_{ballast} is the volume of the ballast material,
- ρ_{ballast} is the density of the ballast material,
- m_{AWE} is the mass of the airborne wind energy (AWE) system installed on the platform,
- V_{immersed} is the immersed volume of the floating system,
- ρ_{water} is the density of water.

The calculated mass distribution includes approximately 31 tons of steel for the hull and 44 tons of heavy sand ballast. The ballast plays a crucial role in ensuring the platform’s stability, increasing its resistance to tilting motions caused by waves and wind forces. Results are summarised in Table 2.

Diameter	Draft	Hull Mass	Ballast Mass
5 m	4.7 m	31 tons	44 tons

Table 2: Dimensions and Masses of the Floating Platforms

The mooring system should provide platform stability, and for the Sicilian site, the catenary configuration is preferred as it is well-suited for intermediate water depths [18].

We sized the mooring lines to withstand aerodynamic and hydrodynamic loads, with a safety factor applied to account for dynamic effects. We then evaluated the holding capacity (HC) and minimum breaking load (MBL) as:

We sized the mooring lines assuming the dominant external action is the aerodynamic traction transmitted by the tether during power production. For a first-order sizing, the design load is approximated as mainly horizontal and aligned with the mean wind direction; possible vertical and dynamic contributions are conservatively included by increasing the aerodynamic load by 20% and by applying a global safety factor.

We define the design load as

$$F_{\text{tot}} = F_{\text{aero}} (1 + \delta), \quad (8)$$

where F_{aero} is the estimated mean aerodynamic traction force and $\delta = 0.2$ accounts for vertical and residual hydrodynamic effects. The holding capacity (HC) and minimum breaking load (MBL) are then evaluated as:

$$HC = F_{\text{tot}}/n_{\text{lines}}$$

$$MBL = HC \cdot SF$$

where:

- F_{tot} is the total design load acting on the station (N),
- n_{lines} is the number of mooring lines (-),
- SF is the global safety factor (-)

Using $F_{\text{aero}} \approx 633$ kN, $\delta = 0.2$, $n_{\text{lines}} = 3$, and $SF = 8$, we obtain $F_{\text{tot}} \approx 760$ kN, $HC \approx 253$ kN per line, and a target $MBL \approx 2.0$ MN per line.

We computed the catenary length l as:

$$l = h \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2T}{W \cdot h} + 1} \quad (9)$$

where T is the tether tension (measured in equivalent tons), h is the sea depth and $W = d^2 K$ is the mass per unit metre: d is the diameter of the mooring line while K is the specific mass per unit volume of the material used [19] [20] .

A line diameter of $d = 50$ mm, with a unit weight of 55 kg/m, is selected. Considering a sea depth of $h=150$ m, we can calculate the total line length, resulting in an estimated total mooring line mass of approximately 81 tons.

Since the catenary mooring configuration primarily induces horizontal forces at the anchoring point, drag anchors are optimal for this scenario due to their high resistance in horizontal loading conditions.

We determined the holding capacity F_{anchor} using the following empirical relation:

$$F_{\text{anchor}} = K_a \cdot (W_{\text{anchor}})^a, \quad (10)$$

where W_{anchor} is the anchor weight, and K_a and a are site-specific constants. For this application, a drag anchor weighing 4 tons is sufficient to meet the required holding capacity of 250 kN per line.

1.3. Transmission System

Since the LCA results will be compared with those of the hypothetical wind farm located along the Sicilian coast studied by Brussa et al. [21], the transmission line selected for the OAWF farm is similar, depicted in Figure 6.

In particular, in Sicily there have been occurrences of overloading events concerning the 220 kV power grid, which currently handles a significant portion of the region's internal power generation. More specifically, issues have been observed along the transmission lines connecting the load centres of Palermo and Messina; therefore, a connection to the 380 kV power grid in Campania has been considered [22].

Figure 6: Submarine transmission line considered in this study, comparable to [21].

We choose to use High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) transmission due to its superior performance over long distances compared to traditional High

Voltage Alternating Current (HVAC) systems. HVDC technology minimizes energy losses, avoids the need for reactive power compensation, and ensures efficient power delivery over extended cable lengths, such as the 690 km required in this case [23]. The system employs voltage source converters for seamless conversion between AC and DC, offering higher system reliability and reduced fault currents compared to line commutated converters.

The connection to the onshore grid targets the 380 kV network to alleviate existing issues in the 220 kV grid, as identified in previous overload events.

The layout of transmission lines and seabed depth has been carefully considered to optimise cable routing and reduce installation complexity. For this reason cables are generally along the coast, characterised by a shallower seabed.

The selected transmission system employs a range of submarine cables tailored to specific sections of the grid:

- Collection System: three-core copper cables with Cross-Linked Polyethylene (XLPE) insulation are used for gathering power from individual platforms at 33 kV AC [24].
- Interconnection Cables: medium-voltage cables (132 kV HVAC) connect offshore substations, featuring copper conductors, lead sheathing, and steel armoring for durability .
- Transmission Line: high-voltage (450 kV HVDC) single-core cables with mass-impregnated insulation and steel armoring are deployed to transport electricity to the onshore grid.

Finally, we considered to use three offshore substations, each one equipped with DC/AC converters and step-up transformers to facilitate the connection between the floating platforms and the onshore grid, sketched in Figure 7. The transformers operate at voltages of 420 kV/380 kV [25].

1.4. Energy Storage

Energy storage is an integral part of the transmission design to address the intermittent nature of wind energy. We choose a battery Energy Storage System (BESS) with Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) batteries for its high efficiency, fast response times, and long lifecycle [26]. Each offshore substation is equipped with a 2 MWh battery pack to provide backup power during reel-in phases of the airborne kites. The batteries are housed

Figure 7: Sketch of the layout of the considered power transmission system.

in climate-controlled environments to maintain optimal operating temperatures, extending their operational lifespan to approximately 10 years.

1.5. *Electric machines*

The selection of the generator is a crucial step to ensure efficient energy conversion. We identified a low-speed, direct-drive Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) as the solution due to its proven reliability and efficiency in renewable energy applications. The generator is designed for a maximum reel-out power of 2 MW.

Key design considerations include the mass of the primary components, such as copper windings (1103 kg), permanent magnets (171 kg), rotor iron (541 kg), and stator iron (1735 kg), resulting in a total generator mass of approximately 3550 kg.

The external-rotor configuration was selected for its enhanced suitability for airborne applications. Standardised parameters such as a copper fill factor of 0.8, a peak airgap flux density of 0.8 T, and a slot height of 75 mm were incorporated to improve the generator's performance and structural integrity.

1.6. Design Results

The overall system efficiency is estimated at 70%, accounting for the combined efficiencies of the transmission cables, power converters, battery storage, and electric motors. Additionally, for the evaluation of the net energy production, is important to consider the capacity factor of 39 % presented in Section 1.1.

The resulting OAWE farm comprises 500 individual systems, each with a nominal power (average over one pumping cycle) of 1 MW, resulting in an estimated net power provided to the grid of 35.872 TWh over the 30-year operational lifetime.

This configuration differs significantly with the offshore horizontal-axis wind turbine (OHAWT) farm analysed by Brussa et al. (2022), which consists of only 190 turbines, each with a nominal power of 14.7 MW.

This preliminary design lays the foundation for the development of the inventory used in the Life Cycle Assessment, and for the cost estimation for the techno economic analysis.

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